

interstore

D6.1 – Report on project identity and website

Work Package 6 – Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation

Task 6.1 – Communication and Dissemination

Submission date: 31 March 2023

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Call	HORIZON-CL5-2022-D3-01
Grant Agreement N°	101096511
Project Start Date	01-01-2023
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PU	Public	x
SEN	Sensitive	
C-UE/EU-C	EU Classified	

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ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

D	Deliverable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
EASE	European Association for Storage of Energy
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
WP	Working Package

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable is a report on the project identity and website of the InterSTORE project. It focuses on activities carried out to define documents and communication tools within the consortium and their dissemination to third parties as well as the European Commission. In addition, the structure of the website of InterSTORE project is presented here.

InterSTORE project is funded under the call HORIZON-CL5-2022-D3-01 and aims to advance the development of the innovative middleware that, while virtualising the storage technology, will simplify its use from the point of view of integration platform thanks to a technology agnostic approach.

The first part of the document details the visual identity of InterSTORE, including the project logo, dissemination materials, and document templates. The visual identity of the project, *via* its colours and secondary elements, aims to simplify the identification of the project by the public. It provides the basis for specific communication and dissemination activities to gain visibility among the target group such as industry, research, and academia, policymakers (via webinars, technical conferences etc.).

The second part focuses on the InterSTORE website, which will support the project's visual identity and serves to function as a reference for a wide audience interested in learning about the project and the progress of its activities. It will communicate the overview of the project, detailed information about its objectives, news, events, and publications of the partners of the project. The purpose of the website is to present, share, and display all the related information about the development of the project and disseminate its results.

This deliverable will be closely linked to D6.2 Dissemination and Communication Plan. As part of this plan, the InterSTORE website will act as one of the key communication tools for online dissemination and communication activity of the project. Social media channels (e.g., Twitter and LinkedIn) will amplify the key messages delivered through the project website. It will reach many different target audiences, including industrial networks and associations, Academia and research, public stakeholders at the EU, national and local levels, other related national and EU-funded projects, media, and the wider public in and beyond Europe.

2 INTRODUCTION

2.1 The purpose of this document

This document falls under the Work Package (WP) 6 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation and reports on the identity of the InterSTORE project and the website. The main objective of this deliverable is to provide the necessary materials to support the efficient realisation of the dissemination and communication activities planned during the project's lifetime, including conferences, newsletters, and publications.

Established InterSTORE project visual identity tools include a logo, document templates, a Brand guidebook with guidance, and a website. The visual identity of the project will reinforce the core aim, objectives, and goals of the project. All the elements will be used throughout the lifetime of the project. Some of the elements will be included in each project's deliverable to allow better identification of the project.

This deliverable is closely linked to D6.2 First Communication and Dissemination Plan, due in Month 6 of the project.

3 Visual Identity

3.1 Logo

The logo of InterSTORE aims at identifying the project. It represents the project in every communication material and activity. Firstly, the logo includes the project's acronym "InterSTORE", we can read the full name "Interoperable open-source Tools to Enable hyRidisation, utiliSation, and moneTisation of stORage flexibility". It simplifies the complex title of the project and makes it more memorable and agile.

Secondly, the logo contains various elements representing the complexity of the project. Three elements - cubes mean that InterSTORE project plans to integrate different platforms by developing innovative software to virtualise storage technologies.

The colour codes of the project are dark blue, purple as well as turquoise blue, typically associated with new technologies, innovations, and sustainability. Based on the colour palette the logo could be used in different variations.

Figure 1: Official InterSTORE logo

Figure 2: InterSTORE logo, dark blue background

Figure 3: InterSTORE logo, purple background

3.1.1 Colour Palette

To represent the InterSTORE project, the following colours were chosen and approved by project consortium: dark blue, purple, turquoise blue.

RGB

6 16 97

#061061

92 82 246

#5f52f6

50 204 218

#32ccda

Figure 4: Color Palette

Gradient transition

92 82 246

50 204 218

Figure 5: "Gradient transition" is used for creating visual designs

3.1.2 Secondary identity

To support visual identity several supporting elements were elaborated including cubes, rhombuses and icons in corresponding colours.

Figure 6: Supporting elements "Cubes" in corresponding colors

Figure 7: Supporting elements "Rhombuses"

Figure 8: Supporting elements "Icons"

3.1.3 Typography

For InterSTORE project, the following three fonts were selected, N27, Arial, and Bahnschrift. N27 is an InterSTORE typeface for print and web applications. Arial and Bahnschrift are standard system typefaces for Microsoft Office applications including emails.

N27

LIGHT ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
 0123456789

MEDIUM ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
 0123456789

Figure 9: Font "N27"

Arial

REGULAR ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
 0123456789

BOLD **ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ**
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
0123456789

Figure 10: Font 'Arial'

Bahnschrift

REGULAR ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
 0123456789

BOLD **ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ**
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
0123456789

Figure 11: Font 'Bahnschrift'

3.2 List of Communication and Dissemination Materials

The communication and dissemination materials where the logo and project identity will be used are the following (non-exhaustive list):

1. Project website;
2. Social media channels;
3. E-Newsletter;
4. All documents developed within the framework of the project and in particular the documents to be submitted to the European Commission such as deliverables, agendas, minutes of meetings, white paper, etc.;
5. PowerPoint presentations used for communication and dissemination activities carried out by consortium partners;
6. Dissemination materials such as brochures, posters, presentation template, brochures, roll-ups, etc.;
7. Physical and online events organized or participated in by the project: workshops, webinars, conferences

3.3 Templates

All the documents developed within the framework of the project and supporting partners' work are subject to a specific format template. The following templates have been developed to be used during the project's lifetime:

1. Deliverable template;
2. Minutes of the meeting template;

3. PowerPoint template;
4. Text template;
5. Letterhead template.

D#.# - Deliverable Title

Work Package Number - Work Package Name
Task Number - Task Name
Submission date of deliverable: Day Month Year

Project Acronym	INTERSTORE
Call	HORIZON-CL5-2022-D3-01
Grant Agreement N°	101096511
Project Start Date	01-01-2023
Project End Date	31-12-2025
Duration	36 months

Figure 12: Deliverable Template

Name of Meeting
Location, 00 Month 202_

MINUTES OF MEETING

Name of the meeting
Work Package Identity
Subtask
Location
Date

REVISION INDEX

Date	Version	Author	Comment
DD-MM-YY	1.0		The first draft
	2.0		Updated version
	FINAL		Final and submitted version

Name of Meeting
Location, 00 Month 202_

ATTENDANCE LIST

DAY 1

Organisation	Name	Signature

Decision:

- Text
- Text

Decision:

- Text
- Text

Decision:

Text

Table 1: Example of Table

Title	Title	Title	Title

Figure 1: Example of Figure

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Figure 13: Minutes of the Meeting Template

Figure 14: Presentation Template

Location, 00 Month 202,

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 1.1.1 Subtopic 2

 1.2 SUBCHAPTER 2

 1.2.1 Subtopic 2

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Figure 15: Text Template

To Name Surname | Company | Code | Date

Dear Name,

[Text]

Sincerely,

Name Surname

Company

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Figure 16: Letterhead Template

4 Project Website

4.1 Structure

The project website of InterSTORE was planned by project partner EASE, in collaboration with the designated representatives of all project partners. Active participation was enabled and all partners contributed to the content. After conducting a thorough market research, EASE decided to engage the company MADE to provide services of visual identity design and technical delivery of project website. MADE is a company specialised in digital design and corporate identities. MADE oversaw building and implementing the website on the online platform WordPress; the content, structure, and guidance were drafted by EASE and the graphics were developed by MADE. The website map conveys all the necessary information about the project and fulfils its need for effective communication and dissemination.

4.1.1 Introduction

The purpose of the InterSTORE website is to reach a wide audience interested in acquiring more knowledge about the project, to help users to understand better the energy sector and to communicate the project aim, objectives, the roles of each partner, the foreseen timeline of work and expected impact. The website will be regularly updated with the progress of the work made within the project, promoting future events and news items on the development of its activities. The website will be managed by EASE, who will oversee, update it as needed and collect inputs and suggestions from partners concerning news and other content to be published on the website.

4.1.2 Domain

The domain of the InterSTORE website will be www.interstore-project.eu, allowing also for the purchase of a related e-mail address, info@interstore.eu. The website is hosted on the platform WordPress, which has a hosting plan included. Web hosting stores the files of the website and makes them accessible to visitors worldwide.

4.1.3 Interface

The website was designed on WordPress which makes it responsive and compatible with a big number of devices, browsers, and screen sizes.

It has enhanced functionality, it is easy to customise, add or adapt the information to the website as well as change sections, pages and subpages of the website. The website of the InterSTORE project will be hosted on WordPress servers, therefore, there is no need to install additional plugins or applications.

4.2 Content

The site map was planned by EASE and consortium partners, it is a user-visible sitemap and hierarchical structure that shows all the content pages, both parent and child. The site map of the website is presented below ([Figure 17](#)).

Figure 17: Site Map of the website

4.2.1 Homepage

The homepage of the website communicates the main aspects of the project and it is divided into the following sections “Learn more about the project” with a short description of the project, the main objectives of the project, and tools developed within the project with corresponding links forwarding to the subpages, Video of the project, “Our partners” with the respective logos of the InterSTORE partners, the Twitter window with the last posts of the project.

Figure 18: Homepage

Figure 19: Objectives of the project – Homepage

Figure 20: Living Labs section – Homepage

LATEST NEWS AND ARTICLES

24 MARCH 2023
Electrical network currently has PV production systems

20 MARCH 2023
InterSTORE Project is Officially Launched

[read more](#)

Figure 21: Latest News and Articles – Homepage

OUR PARTNERS

Figure 22: Our Partners Section - Homepage

Figure 23: Events section and Disclaimer - Homepage

The header of the website contains a menu that leads to other sections of the website such as: “About”, “Tools”, “Living Labs”, “News & Articles”, “Events”, “Resources”, “Contact us”, LinkedIn and Twitter accounts. The footer included the EU flag and disclaimer.

4.2.2 About page

The “About” section is divided into two subpages “InterSTORE project” and “Our partners”.

The “InterSTORE project” page includes a description of the project, its goals, and the timeline of the project.

InterSTORE is an EU-funded project that aims to deploy and demonstrate a set of interoperable Open-Source tools to integrate Distributed Energy Storage (DES) and Distributed Energy Resources (DER), to enable the hybridization, utilisation and monetisation of storage flexibility, within a real-life environment.

[about](#) [tools](#) [living Labs](#) [news and articles](#) [events](#) [resources](#) [contact us](#)

InterSTORE plans to address the complexity of varying characteristics of storage solutions and technologies by developing an innovative middleware that, while virtualising the storage technology, will simplify its use from the point of view of integration platform thanks to a technology agnostic approach.

The middleware will facilitate the integration of storage creating an independence from hardware solutions which are critical from customer perspectives to avoid vendor lock-in solutions. It will also facilitate its use from a monetisation perspective making sure that more investments in storage are enabled.

The goals of the InterSTORE:

- Provide 4 software open-source tools for assuring interoperability, flexibility and data standardization
- Consider each relevant aspect of flexible use of HESS in different main application areas (EV, Industrial, Residential, Commercial)
- Demonstrate 7 high impact use cases in 4 real life living labs
- Use beyond the state-of-the-art methods to enable hybridization, utilisation and monetisation of storage flexibility, while also ensuring data space standardization

Figure 24: InterSTORE project page

The “Our partners” page contains information about the partners, their logos and the links to their web pages.

OUR PARTNERS

Figure 25: Our partners page

4.2.3 Tools

The aim of the InterSTORE project is to deliver a set of interoperable Open-Source tools to integrate Distributed Energy Storage (DES) and Distributed Energy Resources (DER), to enable the hybridization, utilisation and monetisation of storage flexibility, within a real-life environment. Based on the importance of a continuous development of these tools that will assure the easy integration of 2030.5 standard protocol by EU inverter manufacturers, it was decided to create a section “Tools” which includes subpages with the related information of each developed tool: “Open-Source Interoperability Software Toolkit”, Testing procedure and software tool, legacy system protocol converter, open data space framework that will be integrated in seven solutions that will be tested within the four InterSTORE living labs.

<p>FIWARE based Energy Campus Management</p> <p>FIWARE is emerging as a reference architecture in different data-intensive applications including energy. The main value of FIWARE is to create data management that can easily go beyond the single silos of Energy. FZJ is experimenting the use of a FIWARE architecture to realize its internal Smart Campus Experiment.</p>	
<p>Home Energy Management System (HEMS)</p> <p>IVESC home Energy Management System is enables flexibility provision from home, working with diverse appliances such as washing machines or heat pumps. Its main functions are monitoring and data analytics on energy usage; optimal scheduling of flexible assets to provide demand side flexibility support.</p>	
<p>Residential/Commercial Power Management</p> <p>Interoperable open-source tools to enable hybridization, utilization, and monetization of energy. InterSTORE flexibility 12 the EMS provides centralized & control of energy assets for the real-time needs that use of renewables is maximized while simultaneously electricity bill and environmental footprint are reduced with limited or no impact on business performance and user experience for commercial and residential buildings. The outcomes of the InterSTORE project will support the development of the next generation energy management systems.</p>	
<p>Hybrid E-mobility Management Platform</p> <p>InterSTORE will contribute to advance the current DES & DER offered by ENELX leveraging from the easy adaptation to standardised protocol to increase the number of supported hybrid DERs (e.g. PHE, load, BESS, and EVs.)</p>	

Figure 26: Tools pages

4.2.4 Living Labs

“Living Labs” section includes four subpages describing each pilot, which has an essential role and authority to carry out the specific activities for the InterSTORE project.

The pilot partners have all the essential roles and authority to carry out the specified activities. They are related to four different application domains, and characterized by geographic, economic, and size diversity to increase scalability and stakeholder impact. Each pilot’s page includes the general information about the Pilot, its objectives and addressed topics.

Industrial Flexibility Pilot Portugal

The Portuguese pilot project will take place at Sonae Campus, in Maia. The Campus is composed of many companies that share the same electrical network fully managed by Capwatt in the command and control center 24/7.

This electrical network currently has PV production systems, several charging points for electric vehicles (AC of 22kW and one DC of 160kW) that feed the fleet of the companies located in the industrial park, and an electric energy storage system of 320kW/798kWh, a 7.4 MWe CHP, among other technologies. In this way, the pilot intends to install a small ESS next to the hub of the electric vehicle chargers and manage the distributed storage, controlling and operating, the ESS already installed, the system to be installed and two more systems (a HESS and an ESS of 2nd life batteries) that are already planned and expected to be installed in the next few years.

At the Campus, it is under development the setup and implementation of a Renewable Energy Community (REC) that will increase the renewable energy penetration, boosting the energy transition.

Sonae Campus
Maia, Portugal

electric energy storage system

320kW/798kWh

Figure 27: Industrial Flexibility Portugal Pilot

The pilot also foresees the use of the ESS next to the EV chargers, to increase the capacity of the electric grid nodes, without the need to change or upgrade the currently installed infrastructures. The battery will be charged when the power supply is lower than what the grid is capable of and discharged when the chargers need more power than the grid can give.

The Living Lab Energy Campus (LLEC) at Forschungszentrum Jülich (FZJ, "Jülich Research Centre") constitutes a testbed where both innovative hardware and software solutions for district energy systems are tested under close to real conditions, in a scientifically monitored environment incorporating real users.

The basis for LLEC is formed by the already existing infrastructure of the FZJ, which is one of the largest interdisciplinary research centers in Europe. The research center forms a self-contained district with few infrastructural connections to the surrounding area.

The main part of the research center in Jülich covers an area of about 1.7 square kilometers with approximately 150 buildings, multiple large test facilities, and supercomputers.

The infrastructure consists of an electricity grid at various voltage levels, a meshed heating grid, various cooling grids, and a gas grid. Within LLEC, different energy demonstrators for both generating and storing energy are integrated into the existing infrastructure in such a way, that the resulting infrastructure forms an ideal testbed for future multi-modal district energy systems with a high share of intermittent renewables energies.

Figure 28: Commercial Flexibility pilot Germany

E-Mobility Flexibility Pilot Italy

X Lab 1 is the testing eld for medium-scale solutions (e. g. middle residential, small commercial and industrial). The laboratory is composed of 2 interconnected microgrids (MGs): 20 kW scale DC MG at 48 VDC that can reach 300 kW if operated at 750 VDC (the nominal voltage is adjustable in the range 48 V – 750 V), 64 kVA scale AC MG.

0-grid (the tested solution is not connected to the main grid) and on-grid (the tested solution is connected to the main grid) testing modes, AC/DC hybrid testing, testing of any AC or DC devices, and interoperability testing are available. Any type of solution/device can be tested: power converters, EESS, e-car charging stations, etc. The lab is completed by two 12 kWp photovoltaic (PV) plants with innovative bifacial Enel 3SUN panels that can reach 14.5 kWp in bifacial way and two (1 AC and 1 DC) regenerative grid simulators.

Figure 29: E-Mobility Flexibility Pilot Italy

Residential Flexibility Pilot Austria

The Austrian pilot would be located in areas of operation for EVN in the region of Lower Austria and within the residential sector. EVN is one of Austria's largest DSO, energy supplier and energy services providers and is coordinating the EU Innovation Fund project Green The Flex (GtF).

Other GtF's project partners, apart from EVN and cyberGRID, are TIKO (heat pumps aggregation) and Fronius (inverters manufacturer). EVN is also the parent company to cyberGRID, leading the InterSTORE Residential Flexibility pilot.

This pilot area was chosen to achieve synergies between this project and the GtF project which plans to aggregate more than 2500 decentralised units until 2025 and use them for ancillary services, making more than 6 MW of power and more than 5 GWh/a short term load shift potential accessible to our energy system as flexibility.

Out of this large aggregation pool, InterSTORE will use approx. 20-30 most suitable DES, forming at least two energy communities, to demonstrate the interoperability toolkit and new generation of Energy Management System functionalities (e.g. enhanced Flexibility Management Platform cyberNOC) used in two use cases (UC1, UC2). The two or more energy communities will be used to compare different operational modes, like market optimization, self-consumption, ex-post accounting and hybrid. InterSTORE: Interoperable open-source tools to enable hybridisation, utilisation, and monetisation of storage flexibility 22 Furthermore, in the integration and testing project phase, cyberGRID will leverage its Smart Grids Laboratory Infrastructure for hosting flexibility management platform and a laboratory setting of smart meters and several RTU/IED devices for simulating, testing and evaluating various demand response, distributed generation and storage configurations, TSO/DSO market bidding and activations, wholesale electricity markets and various use cases.

Figure 30: Residential Flexibility Pilot Austria

4.2.5 News and Articles

The page “News & Articles” contains all the latest news regarding the project and its partners, as well as publications in the framework of the project.

Figure 31: News and Articles Page

4.2.6 Events

The “Events” section provides an overview of upcoming events, either open for public or just limited to the Consortium, such as General Assembly, and Plenary Session meetings in which the general public cannot participate but can read about its outcomes regarding the project and partners.

Figure 32: Events page

4.2.7 Resources

The section “Communication Materials” provides all the communication materials used for communication and dissemination reasons within the project, such as leaflets, posters, etc.

Figure 33: Resources page

4.2.8 Contact us

This final page “Contact us” will contain the form which users could fill in to get in contact with project partners.

Contact us

info@interstore.eu

Follow us:

LinkedIn / Twitter

Figure 34: Contact us page

4.3 Website Statistics

The InterSTORE website statistics will be monitored through the Google Analytics platform, which allows the tracking of the website performance and planning of a reactive communication strategy. Personal data of internauts will be processed according to [the GDPR Regulation](#) (Regulation 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council, 27th April 2016). Google Analytics allows the analysis of various data aspects of website performance. Results from the platform will be available and shared with the Consortium at all meetings to assist the discussions on strategies on how to increase the project's outreach.

4.4 Social Media

InterSTORE Social Media accounts (LinkedIn and Twitter) were created in January 2023. They aim at promoting news, activities and outcomes of the project by gathering an online community of users.

The corresponding icons are presented in several sections of the website, as they are always pinned in the header of the page. The icons are linked to the accounts. For the social media channels, the built-in analytics tool will provide information on the followers' growth, the

engagement rate and the conversations around the project and the topics. This information will provide data on the awareness of the audience on the project.

4.4.1 LinkedIn

The URL of the LinkedIn account is <https://www.linkedin.com/company/interstoreproject/>

LinkedIn profile name is InterSTORE. It will be used to strengthen the relationship between parties and development of new connections among several interested actors.

InterSTORE

Interoperable open-source tools to enable hybridisation, utilisation, and monetisation of storage flexibility.
Services for Renewable Energy · 38 followers

Figure 35: LinkedIn page of the InterSTORE project

4.4.2 Twitter

The URL of the Twitter account is [InterSTORE \(@InterSTORE_eu\) / Twitter](https://twitter.com/InterSTORE_eu)

The Twitter account will be used to provide tweets related to all project's research activities, project's news, and to re-tweet any subjects related to their activity and to the related topic.

Figure 36: Twitter page of the InterSTORE project

4.5 Privacy and Cookie Policy

The Secretariat of EASE is run by CLERENS NV/SA (VAT n° BE0791 153 081) who is the data controller, responsible for processing your personal data in accordance with the **GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation)**.

Please **[click here](#)** for more details regarding the **[Privacy Policy](#)** and **[Cookie Policy](#)**.

5 Conclusion

Through the InterSTORE website and Social Media accounts, the project's information and outcomes will be communicated and disseminated, along with other information relevant within its framework. The progress and updates from the project Consortium will gradually be implemented into the website.

EASE will regularly update the pages and subpages of the website, upload relevant materials, and publish news items, as well as related events and project news. Only by maintaining the site updated, it is possible to ensure a high outreach potential for the project communication and dissemination. The website also reports its effectiveness to EC and the whole project consortium.

The website and related statistics will comply with Data Protection Policy. Throughout the project's lifetime, the usability of the website will be reviewed to bring further improvements.

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